

“MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE PREVENTION OF CRIMES INVOLVING MINORS IN MISCONDUCT”

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ABSTRACT

Crimes related to the involvement of minors in prostitution in Uzbekistan remain one of the most pressing social problems. The article analyzes the ongoing legal and organizational measures to prevent this type of crime, identifies the shortcomings of current legislation and makes proposals for their improvement. The opinions of various scientists are also compared and the author's personal views are highlighted. The results of the study will serve to develop proposals aimed at strengthening the legal protection of minors and improving the effectiveness of prevention.

Currently, crimes related to the involvement of minors in prostitution are manifested as a serious social and legal problem not only in Uzbekistan, but also throughout the world. Such crimes have a destructive impact on the spiritual and physical health of the younger generation and pose a serious threat to the spiritual foundations of society.

Although the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child," and other regulatory legal acts guarantee the legal protection of minors, in practice, a number of problems persist in this area. In particular, the involvement in prostitution using modern information technologies, the covert nature of crimes, and the insufficient discussion of such issues in society reduce the effectiveness of preventive measures.

This article discusses the analysis of legal, organizational, and social measures used to prevent crimes related to the involvement of minors in prostitution, identifying existing problems, and developing proposals for their elimination.

Paragraph "a" of part 3 of Article 131 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for criminal liability for involving minors in prostitution, creating conditions for such activity, or providing them with assistance. This article is directly aimed at ensuring the rights of children, who are considered the most vulnerable segments of society.

In fact, the legal nature of this crime indicates its double social danger. On the one hand, it harms the physical and moral health of the minor. On the other hand, it negatively affects the spiritual and moral foundations of society, the institution of the family, and the upbringing of youth.

The legal aspects of involving minors in prostitution are characterized by:

- Special age-related structural features: the victim's age is taken into account as an aggravating circumstance of the crime.

- Helping or creating conditions is also a criminal act. For example, actions such as allocating housing, providing transportation, or finding clients also entail criminal liability.

Additional actions: often involvement in prostitution is carried out not only through violence or threats, but also through deception, promises of material assistance, and exploitation of needs.

From a social point of view, these crimes arise under the influence of the following factors:

- Lack of control in the family and educational shortcomings;
- Poverty, economic problems and unemployment;
- Negative impact of information technologies: gaining the trust of young people through false information and valuable gifts on social networks;
- Lack of education and low level of legal culture.

International norms also strictly prohibit the involvement of children in prostitution. For example, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child requires states to protect children from any form of exploitation [1]. According to International Labour Organization Convention No. 182, involvement in prostitution is defined as the worst form of child labor. [2]

In local legal acts, the protection of children from prostitution is ensured as follows:

- The Law "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" (2008) defines the state's obligations to protect the spiritual and physical health of children.
- The Law "On Protection of the Reproductive Health of the Population" (2019) also defines issues of promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people.

In recent years, some disclosed cases related to the involvement of minors in prostitution in Uzbekistan have caused widespread public discussion. For example, in 2024, in the Khorezm region, a case of involving a 16-year-old girl in prostitution by various individuals with promises of financial assistance was exposed.

Such cases also indicate the latent nature of this type of crime and the fact that victims, due to their age, often fear contacting law enforcement agencies.

Also, the results of the analysis of the psychological portrait of the perpetrators of the crime show that they often exploit the social needs of minors, not only material needs, but also the need for love and attention.[4]

In Uzbekistan, the issue of preventing crimes related to the involvement of minors in prostitution is one of the important directions of state policy. For this purpose, various preventive measures are being carried out by law enforcement agencies, educational institutions, non-governmental organizations, and the media.

However, a number of problems persist in practice. These include:

Unsystematic nature of preventive measures. In most cases, preventive campaigns are one-time or short-term. For example, spirituality lessons or preventive meetings held in schools or colleges are often conducted in a formal spirit and do not leave a deep impression on young people. Their regularity and methodology are not sufficiently developed.[5]

Moreover, some preventive work is carried out only after the commission of the offense, that is, it remains in the form of "reaction," not prevention.

Insufficient cooperation between organizations. The Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Public Education, the Committee on Mahalla and Family Issues, the media, and NGOs participate in the protection of minors from prostitution. However, their actions are often uncoordinated. For example, a problem identified at a school may not be communicated in a timely manner to the prevention inspector of the area, or the exchange of information with mahalla officials may be delayed.[6]

This reduces the possibility of early detection of situations that can lead to the involvement of a minor in prostitution.

Cases occurring via the Internet and the problem of control. In recent years, there has been an increase in cases of deception through social networks and messengers when involving minors in prostitution.[7] For example, in Tashkent in 2023, a case was identified where a 17-year-old girl was offered "model" work and subsequently involved in prostitution.[8]

Such activity on the Internet is difficult to control, since such "verbovka" is often carried out through closed groups and personal communication.

Victims' fear of appealing. In practice, minors often do not contact law enforcement agencies out of fear, shame, or fear of their parents' anger. This situation is especially noticeable in the provinces. Therefore, crimes remain hidden or are exposed too late.

Some shortcomings in the legislation. Criminal Code

Although Article 131 establishes liability, there is no special law or state program on prevention. Existing documents are general in nature and do not cover specific mechanisms.[9]

According to statistics, more than 100 cases of involving a minor in prostitution were identified in the Republic during 2022, 2023, and 2024, most of which were young people who grew up in a poor or dysfunctional family environment.[10]

One of the most distressing aspects is that in the above-mentioned cases, more than 80% of the victims were girls aged 15-17 years.[11]

A number of scientists point to ignorance and a lack of open communication with young people as the main shortcoming of prevention in this area. For example, as the legal scholar H. Karimov noted:

"When young people's legal awareness and culture are low, they fall into the hands of criminals more quickly. Promotion and education should be central to prevention." [12]

Effective prevention can be achieved through systematic analysis of problems in practice, systematization of preventive measures, protection of youth using information technologies, and raising legal culture.

On this issue, various scholars, lawyers, and specialists in the field have different views on the causes of involvement in prostitution and measures for its prevention.

According to legal scholar Sh. Rakhimov, the main reason is the economic situation and unemployment. She believes that as a result of poverty and economic hardship, young people are easily influenced by promises of financial aid.[13]

Another scientist, criminologist B. Khalikov, considers it a shortcoming to link the cause only to the economic aspect. He argues that the spiritual emptiness of young people, their lack of education, and the weakness of upbringing in the family are also among the main reasons.[14]

In our opinion, it is correct not to separate these two views from each other, but to consider them interconnected. Because the fact that a minor falls into the hands of criminals is usually influenced not by one, but by several factors - material, moral, and informational environment.

Scientists also have different views on the issue of prevention. For example, researcher A. Matkuliyeu believes that preventive measures should be carried out through legal education, and emphasizes that increasing legal knowledge among young people and ensuring their awareness of their rights plays an important role in preventing involvement in prostitution.[15]

According to another scholar, pedagogue Z. Abdullayeva, spiritual education is paramount, and the scholar believes that "knowing the law is not enough, it is possible to distance young people from such mistakes by forming in their hearts the values of chastity, love for the Motherland, and family"16.

In my opinion, both aspects are important in this regard: both legal knowledge and moral education yield effective results only when implemented in interconnection. For example, in schools, it is not enough to limit oneself to just conducting conversations about the law or just a lesson on spirituality. This requires an open conversation with young people, based on communication, and influencing them through real-life examples.

In our opinion, such tasks as preventing the involvement of young people in prostitution, increasing the legal knowledge and awareness of young people, strengthening their internal position through spiritual and educational work, protecting them on the Internet, and creating systems for identifying groups and individuals of threats can only be achieved. Only then will prevention be effective and it will be possible to protect future generations from this crime.

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